

Democracy by Default - Hatching a Commons for Digital Deliberation

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Abstract

This paper discusses how the democratic governance of communities, community-owned infrastructures, and digital commons can be organized based on dynamic and fluid deliberation processes using socio-technical protocols. The use of protocols, even though they are “hard to study and easy to ignore” (Rao et al. 2023), is in fact not such a new idea, but has been part of the utopia of the internet from its very beginning: a system of frictionless global communication and instant access to the knowledge of humanity—a “dream of scale and ease” (Lu 2023). In today’s digital society, however, the technical systems that enable participation in public discourse, access to knowledge and information, and building communities are increasingly relying on proprietary infrastructure governed by opaque entanglements between humans and algorithms. This entanglement has increased with the development of large language models (LLMs) that shape user experiences as a “multiverse of echo chambers” (Lu 2023), giving rise to the “algorithmic internet.” People have less power over the design and governance of these infrastructures and their own data and algorithms. What can be done to empower communities and give users control over algorithms, data, and infrastructure? How can we design and build systems that are “democratic by design”?

An ontology is a formal representation of a set of concepts and their relationships within a given domain. The challenge in building democratic socio-technical systems is often rooted in the translation of different ontologies and vocabularies between the engineering, social sciences, and humanities (Callon 1987). Technical systems rely on ontologies of language, objects, and functions. Social systems rely on concepts of power, communication, identity, and relationships, as well as culture and history. Understanding these two realms of knowledge, not as separate systems with their own ontology, but instead as assemblages, helps to shift the focus on associations and relations between humans and nonhumans in the study of technology. Ontologies of social norms can then provide a structured and organized framework for understanding the complex web of social guidelines that govern human behavior in association with technology.

Recent approaches to this problem suggested that protocols can function as a method to translate between these different realms of thinking and find solutions to coordination problems in digital society (Rao et al. 2023). In this paper, we present a framework that uses a protocol-based approach to transform ontologies of social norms into actionable agendas for the development of technical systems. After introducing key concepts for deliberative structures and governance processes, we argue that hatching a Commons for digital deliberation shapes the role of a *governor-engineer* (Zhang 2025). We show how this role is crucial for transforming a theoretical social framework into actionable steps and cultivating a process of techno-scientific governance

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(Fritsch 2020). A cultural build (Deschermayer 2022) then is grounded in principles for commons stewardship, which include Ostrom's commons principles in the nurturing of cultural processes. Hatching is the initial phase in creating the Commons: "Engineering any complex system is a consideration of its initialization conditions—in a Commons, we call these initial conditions the 'Hatch'. [...] because new paradigms sometimes require new terminology to avoid misconceptions and the connotations of old vocabulary." Understood in this way, protocols can help to advance socio-technical systems that are democratic by design. In summary, we envision the co-creation and cultivation of software-mediated systems as a deliberative practice grounded in interdisciplinary research between engineering circles and social scientists.

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